

A Descriptive Study of Different Modes of Assessment among Phase-1 MBBS StudentsShabnam S¹, Manasa D R², Gouramma Huggi³, Srinivas R Deshpande⁴, Avinash S S⁵, Gurupadagoud N Patil⁶, Peersab M Pinjar⁷¹Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology, Chikkaballapura Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkaballapura, Karnataka, India⁴Professor and Head, Department of Biochemistry, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India⁶Tutor, Department of Biochemistry, Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru, Karnataka, India⁷Professor, Department of General Medicine, S S Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre, Davangere, Karnataka, India

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** One of the cornerstones of competency based medical education (CBME) curriculum is assessment as per dictum "assessment drives learning" which involves introduction of various assessment methods like writing skills, OSPE, multiple choice questions (MCQs), viva etc among medical students. Assessment and evaluation are the most important components of medical education which focuses mainly on improving learning of the students.**Aims and Objectives:** To determine and to evaluate the most preferred method of assessment among first year MBBS students.**Materials and methods:** The study was conducted among 150 students studying in first MBBS. Student's performance in first internals was assessed by different methods of assessments like writing skills, OSPE, MCQs, viva, etc and were informed about the purpose of the study.**Results:** Among all different assessment methods, 82% of the students preferred OSPE to score good marks (76-100%) over other methods of assessment. Writing skill denotes the depth of presentation but medical students cannot overlook importance of traditional writing skill which is the least preferred method to score the marks.**Conclusion:** The study concludes that, OSPE could be a preferred method followed by Viva in comparison to other methods for better understanding, easy way of learning and higher order of thinking which highlights the importance of skill lab establishment. MCQs and writing skills need to be improved. Student assessment is a comprehensive process related to teaching learning effectiveness and helps in developing educational concept.**Keywords:** CBME, OSPE, MCQs.

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Introduction

Medical education has become more scientific with introduction of various new teaching learning methods. Assessment plays a pivotal role in implementation of curriculum based medical education (CBME). CBME curriculum is mainly designed to create doctors with sufficient knowledge, attitude, counseling, communication and analytical skills. CBME learning is mainly performance based

learning where a student attains various skills which can be effectively evaluated by introduction of various assessment methods like writing skills, OSPE, MCQs, viva, etc. Assessment is a collective term that assesses a number of competencies at a time. Writing skills in the form of continuous internal assessment (IA) helps in achievement of competencies. To target the multiple competencies and

multiple domains of learning such as cognitive, affective and psychomotor, IA needs to be frequent and multifaceted.

Multiple assessment methods improve the content related evidence for validity and give more information to the teacher about the learning level and needs of the students [1]. In new curriculum a part of assessment of knowledge can be done with MCQs. Higher domains in the cognitive domain can also be assessed by MCQs [2]. Objective assessment of practical skills can be done by implementation of objectively structured practical examination (OSPE), which consists of sets of stations with predesigned skills where an examiner scores the student on a structured checklist. This method of assessment helps in standardizing and uniformly assessing all the students [3]. A viva assesses student’s knowledge of a subject, their communication skills and professional attitude. Different assessment methods provide an opportunity for the facilitators to identify the needs of learner so as to plan remedial measures by providing innovative learning opportunities.

Objectives: To determine and to evaluate the most preferred method of assessment among first year MBBS students.

Materials and Methodology:

The present study was conducted among 150 students studying in first MBBS of 2023-24 batch at Chikkamagaluru Institute of Medical Sciences, Chikkamagaluru.

They were in the age group of 18-20 years. None of them were suffering from any major psychiatric or medical illness. Student’s performance in first internals was assessed by different methods of assessments like writing skills, OSPE, MCQs, viva, etc and were informed about the purpose of the study. Students consent was taken.

Statistical Analysis:

The data was inputted into an Excel spreadsheet and descriptive statistics were computed for both the explanatory and outcome variables. For quantitative variables, measures such as the mean and standard deviation were utilized, while qualitative variables were summarized using frequencies and proportions.

An ANOVA test was employed to assess the statistical significance of variations in assessment methods among the study subjects. Additionally, a post hoc test was conducted to examine mean differences between the various assessment methods.

Result:

Table 1: Shows percentage wise scoring of students for different methods of assessment

Grades of assessment (n – 150)	Writing skill (100 marks)		Viva (20 marks)		MCQ (20 marks)		OSPE (40 marks)	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Very poor (< 25 %)	16	10.7	5	3.3	6	4.0	0	0
Poor (26-50 %)	108	72.0	30	20.0	60	40.0	0	0
Moderate (51-75 %)	26	17.3	96	64.0	68	45.3	27	18.0
Good (76-100 %)	0	0.0	19	12.7	16	10.7	123	82.0
Total	150	100.0	150	100.0	150	100.0	150	100.0

Figure 1: Shows percentage wise scoring of students for different methods of assessment

Table 2: Shows mean, standard deviation and p value for different methods of assessment

Assessment method	Mean	Std. Dev	p value*
Writing skills (%)	40.53	11.01	0.00
Viva (%)	60.00	15.86	
MCQ (%)	56.27	16.03	
OSPE (%)	82.65	7.78	

Figure 2: Shows mean and standard deviation for different methods of assessment

Table 3: Shows mean differences, standard error and p value between the various assessment methods

Post Hoc test (Bonferroni)						
Methods of assessment		Mean Difference	Std. Error	p value	95% CI	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Writing skills (%)	Viva (%)	-19.5	1.52	0.00	-23.48	-15.45
	MCQ (%)	-15.7	1.52	0.00	-19.75	-11.72
	OSPE (%)	-42.1	1.52	0.00	-46.13	-38.10
Viva (%)	MCQ (%)	3.7	1.52	0.08	-0.28	7.75
	OSPE (%)	-22.7	1.52	0.00	-26.67	-18.63
MCQ (%)	OSPE (%)	-26.4	1.52	0.00	-30.40	-22.37

Table 1 and Bar diagram 1: Shows percentage wise scoring of students for different methods of assessment. Among all different assessment methods, 82% of the students preferred OSPE to score good marks (76-100%) followed by viva (64%) and MCQs (45.3%) to score moderate marks over other methods of assessment.

Table 2 and Bar diagram 2: Shows mean, standard deviation and p value for different methods of assessment. OSPE has maximum mean (82.85%) followed by Viva (60%), MCQs (56.27%) and the theory writing skills (40.53%) with significant p value (82.85 %).

Table 3: Shows mean differences, standard error and p value between the various assessment methods with a standard error of 1.52 and significant p value.

Writing skill denotes the depth of presentation but medical students cannot overlook importance of

traditional writing skill which is the least preferred method to score the marks.

Discussion

The present study shows that majority of the students were in favor of OSPE to score good marks as it is credible, effective, interesting and practical-ly oriented method of assessment. OSPE performance stations demonstrates the “shows how” level of Miller framework, while response stations assess the “knows” (principles, theories and recall of facts) and “knows how” (problem analyzing, application and interpretation) [4].

Our study is in correlation with the various studies. Mard SA, Ghafouri S shows that students were in favour of OSPE which can improve learning as well as increasing student’s satisfaction [5]. In another study conducted by Epstein RM, Hundert EM concludes that, in addition to assessments of basic skills, new formats that assess clinical

reasoning, expert judgment, management of ambiguity, professionalism, time management, learning strategies, and teamwork promise a multidimensional assessment while maintaining adequate reliability and validity [6]. Study done by V Wass, C Van Vleuten, J Shatzer, R Jones et al tells that the goal of assessment in medical education remains the development of reliable measurements of student performance which, as well as having predictive value for subsequent clinical competence also have a formative, educational role [7]. C Van Vleuten in his study summarised that final examinations seem to be changing gradually to include more relevant tasks and skills that are appropriate for the graduating medical student [8].

Conclusion

The study concludes that, OSPE could be a preferred method followed by Viva in comparison to other methods for better understanding, easy way of learning and higher order of thinking which highlights the importance of skill lab establishment. MCQs and writing skills need to be improved. Student assessment is a comprehensive process related to teaching learning effectiveness and helps in developing educational concept. CBME learning mainly focus on teacher- student interaction so that the learning of the student becomes more accurate as per dictum "Assessment derives learning". Assessments also provides the opportunity for the students about their performance and their weakness, so that students motivated to correct their mistakes.

References

1. Badyal DK, Singh S, Singh T. Construct validity and predictive utility of internal assessment in undergraduate medical education. *Natl Med J India* 2017; 30:151-4.
2. Badyal DK, Sharma M. Internal Assessment in New MBBS Curriculum: Methods and Logistics. *Intrnl J of Applied and Basic Med Res* 2020; 10(2):68-75.
3. Gruppen LD, Davis WK, Fitzgerald JT, McQuillan MA. Number of stations, and examination length in an objective structured clinical examination. In: Scherpbier AJ, van der Vleuten CP, Rethans JJ, van der Steeg AF, editors. *Advances in Medical Education*. Dordrecht: Springer; 1997.
4. Lakshmipathy K. MBBS student perceptions about physiology subject teaching and objective structured practical examination based formative assessment for improving competencies. *Adv Physiol Educ*. 2015; 39(3):198–204. doi:10.1152/advan.00073.2014.
5. Objective Structured Practical Examination in Experimental Physiology Increased Satisfaction of Medical Students. *Adv in Med Educ and pract* 2020; 11: 651-659.
6. Epstein RM and Hundert EM. Defining and assessing clinical competence, *JAMA* 2002; 387:226-35.
7. Wass, Cees Van der Vleuten, John Shatzer, Roger Jones. Assessment of clinical competence. *The Lancet* 2001; 357:945-49.
8. Vleuten va der CPM. Validity of final examination in undergraduate medical traning. *BMJ* 2000; 321:1217-19.